

CURRENT METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

This scientific article examines modern methods and technologies that contribute to teaching students foreign languages. At present, the issue of new opportunities and technologies in the field of education is very relevant. Innovations concern not only technical means, but also new approaches and methods of teaching. Knowledge of foreign languages allows you to build a successful career, regardless of your geographical location.

Key words: foreign languages, modern technologies, teaching methods, cultural approach, personality-oriented approach, competence-based approach.

Learning foreign languages has become popular due to the globalization process. Modern methods and technologies that help in teaching students a foreign language. Currently, the issue of new opportunities and technologies in the field of education is relevant. Innovations concern not only technical means, but also new approaches and methods of teaching. Knowledge of several foreign languages allows you to build a successful career around the world, opens up new opportunities in communication. A variety of modern methods allows students to receive an education, taking into account the individual abilities of the student and goals in the future.

In all universities of the CIS countries, modern methods of teaching foreign languages are based on a variety of approaches and are implemented within the framework of carefully developed methods that confirm their effectiveness. Theoretical foundations and practical algorithms for teaching have been developed and presented by both domestic and foreign authors [1, p. 56].

"The teaching method" is thoroughly developed a whole complex of different techniques and methods for achieving the goals of learning and teaching. Teaching methods can be classified as didactic means of transferring knowledge and skills, tied to the interaction of the teacher and students. Teaching methods are aimed at the alternate interaction of the teacher and students during classes in order to transfer knowledge from the teacher to the students [4, p.41]

By "learning technology", experts mean the latest direction, which opens up conceptual possibilities for teaching various disciplines. Learning technology is a means of implementing a student-centered approach, where students are required to actively participate during classes.

In modern methods of teaching foreign languages, the following teaching technologies are considered relevant [3, p. 37]:

1. Group learning. Group work in the classroom is an effective method of teaching a foreign language. All students must complete certain tasks together, communicate and interact with each other. The uniqueness of this technology is that language learning can be integrated into the process itself, i.e. students can communicate in a foreign language, do exercises on literacy, pronunciation, etc. together.

2. This method is based on the idea of students working together in lessons, where they are responsible not only for their own success, but also for the success of the entire group. Unlike traditional and individual learning, where each student acts alone and is responsible only for himself, team learning encourages interaction and cooperation between students, teacher and group, emphasizing collective achievements in the learning process.

3. Student-centered learning is a technology that is focused on student initiative. The essence of the technology is the ways to reveal the potential of each student and establish a favorable atmosphere during learning.

4. Distance learning (online education) is characterized by the use of telecommunications for communication between teacher and student, which has become very popular recently because it is very convenient for everyone. The ability to study using the Internet allows you to simplify the learning process and use interactive learning methods.

5. "Language portfolio". It is a set of tools for assessing students' knowledge and skills. In the field of teaching foreign languages, the concept of "language portfolio" appeared from the field of psychology.

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This technology is used to make students more autonomous in learning foreign languages, to give them the opportunity to improve their language competence [5, p. 462].

6. Computer technologies. Allows the use of various computer programs and platforms in classes, with the help of which the learning process becomes more interesting and informative. Now all schools and universities use computer technologies to make learning more effective.

Today, the possibilities of computer technology include a variety of educational programs, among which we can highlight Duolingo, which pays special attention to all language skills, the development of speech skills, control programs for assessing language knowledge and programs that introduce the socio-cultural aspects of the country where the language is being studied.

Within the framework of the computer training course, various visual aids are used as effectively as possible. With the development of the Internet, the possibilities of using computers for teaching foreign languages have increased.

Thus, thanks to new technologies in education, online conferences, communication via instant messengers, audio-voiceover of text, as well as distance learning and testing are possible.

To sum up, it can be stated that the introduction of Internet technologies and artificial intelligence into the study of foreign languages has opened up limitless possibilities, making it more interesting for modern students, as well as more effective due to new, accessible means.

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